

Historical Perspectives on Whistleblowing and Speak-up Culture in the British Armed Forces

Research Briefing

Abstract

This research briefing applies a historical perspective to argue that it is possible to foster a speak-up culture in the British armed forces based on a history of active military engagement with the press in the nineteenth century. The author is a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow at LMU Munich. These findings are based on a two-year research project on the nineteenth-century army serving in India.

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Executive Summary

- Recent reports by the Defence Committee and the Service Complaints Ombudsman for the Armed Forces have identified a negative attitude to complaint in the British Armed Forces and have expressed the need for cultural change.
- The history of the British Armed Forces demonstrates that, despite its hierarchical nature, there is a long tradition of speaking up within the military sector.
- Whereas in the present, the army is often regarded as a space of exception where the usual rules of accountability and transparency do not apply, in the past, people did not accept these distinctions.
- The history of the nineteenth-century army therefore challenges many common-sense assumptions about the relationship between army and society, suggesting that there is potential for change in the future.

Background

One of the fundamental challenges facing modern democracies is how to achieve the appropriate balance between transparency and national security. Openness is a prerequisite for political accountability, but certain kinds of information are too dangerous to circulate freely. Everyone agrees that some information must remain secret; the question is, how best to protect this sensitive information, while still guaranteeing openness and accountability at the highest levels of government.

Military personnel are uniquely affected by this tension. Members of the security and intelligence services are subject to a stricter legal regime than other Crown servants because they are likely to encounter highly privileged information in the course of their duties; they therefore have a unique responsibility to keep this information safe. In the United Kingdom, their special status is reflected in the Official Secrets Act, which specifies that for them any unlawful disclosure relating to security or intelligence is an offence, whereas for other Crown servants and government contractors, the disclosure must be deemed 'damaging' to constitute an offence.¹

Even so, it is precisely because of their important role in upholding national security that military personnel can become important sources of public information. Members of the security and intelligence services are well placed to become critical witnesses. Their information can enable citizens to judge whether government is adhering to its proclaimed values.

How can we ensure that military personnel speak up when they need to, without putting lives at risk? Different solutions to this problem have been proposed. Legal

¹ Gail Bartlett and Michael Everett, *The Official Secrets Act and Official Secrecy*, Briefing Paper Number CBP04722, May 2017, <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-7422/>, accessed 4 November 2024, p. 4.

experts have recommended the introduction of a public interest defence which would remove criminal liability for individuals who could demonstrate that their disclosure was made in the public interest.² The establishment of a statutory commission to receive evidence of serious wrongdoing has also been suggested as a channel for confidentially investigating and resolving concerns.³

For these reforms to take effect, however, a cultural change is also needed. Successive Service Complaints Ombudsmen for the Armed Forces have indicated, in their annual reports, that the service complaints system is not working.⁴ In their 2019 report, *Fairness without Fear: The Work of the Service Complaints Ombudsman*, the Defence Committee identified a negative culture towards complaint; according to their findings, personnel expressed a lack of faith in the system, and a fear that complaining might negatively affect their career.⁵ In her oral evidence session with the Defence Committee in October 2020, former Ombudsman Nicola Williams declared that there needed to be a cultural change within the armed forces to encourage personnel to speak out.⁶ The annual armed forces continuous attitudes survey, published in May 2024, reports that 87% of personnel who experienced bullying, discrimination, or harassment did not make a complaint.⁷

These negative attitudes to complaint may affect personnel's willingness to speak up on issues of national and international significance. Individuals who are unwilling to complain about their conditions of service may also hesitate to disclose information about illegality or inefficiency witnessed in the workplace. In a 2019 workshop organized by the Whistleblowing International Network and the European Organisation of Military Associations and Trade Unions, attendees questioned whether it is even possible to implement a speak-up culture within rigidly hierarchical institutions like the armed forces.⁸

From a historical perspective, the answer to this question is yes. There is a long tradition of speaking out within the British armed forces. Military personnel have historically been active participants in public debate, as well as important sources of

² Matrix Chambers and Mischcon de Reya LLP, *Introducing a Public Interest Defence Briefing Paper*, November 2020, <https://www.matrixlaw.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Introducing-a-Public-Interest-Disclosure-Defence-amended-version.pdf>, accessed 20 September 2024; Law Commission, *Protection of Official Data Report*, September 2020, <https://lawcom.gov.uk/project/protection-of-official-data/>, accessed 20 September 2024, p. 162.

³ Same as above.

⁴ Louisa Brooke-Holland, *The Service Complaints System Commons Library Research Briefing*, August 2024, <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-9153/>, accessed 20 September 2024, p. 15.

⁵ Defence Committee, *Fairness without Fear: The Work of the Service Complaints Ombudsman*, August 2019, <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201919/cmselect/cmdfence/153/15302.htm>, accessed 20 September 2024.

⁶ Defence Committee, Oral evidence: Work of the Service Complaints Ombudsman, 13 October 2020, <https://committees.parliament.uk/event/1821/formal-meeting-oral-evidence-session/>, accessed 20 September 2024, q7.

⁷ Armed Forces Continuous Attitudes Survey, *Armed Forces Continuous Attitudes Survey 2024 Main Report*, May 2024, <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/armed-forces-continuous-attitude-survey-2024>, accessed 20 September 2024.

⁸ EUROMIL and Whistleblowing International Network, *Demystifying Whistleblowing in the Armed Forces*, 2019, <https://euromil.org/demystifying-whistleblowing-in-the-armed-forces/>, accessed 20 September 2024, p. 15.

public information. For much of the nineteenth century, military authorities were reluctant to constrain soldiers' freedom of speech. Prohibitions on writing to the press were slow to be introduced and unevenly enforced. This history of military engagement with the press, spanning nearly two hundred years, demonstrates not only that a speak-up culture is possible within the military, but that for a long time, it was the reality.

This history of speak-up culture within the armed forces challenges common assumptions about the relationship between the military and civil society. Rather than treating the military as a realm of exception that is fundamentally distinct from civil society, history demonstrates that the two can work in sync. Through this history, we learn to challenge the status quo, and to envision alternative realities. After all, our ideas about the past shape our assumptions about what is possible in the future. Because historical knowledge constitutes part of our shared 'common sense', History as a discipline has the power to inform our responses to problems in the present. To quote philosopher Robert Chapman, history 'can help us imagine new worlds. Perhaps more rarely, it can help us see how to bring these worlds into being.'⁹ In this case, greater awareness of the history of active citizenship in the nineteenth-century armed forces can support and inform cultural changes in the present.

Evidence and Analysis

Soldiers have always been important purveyors of public information. From their inception in the seventeenth century, British newspapers regularly printed letters written by soldiers.¹⁰ This practice reflected the limited resources available to early newspaper editors at a time when professional correspondents did not yet exist. So-called 'special correspondents' did not become a permanent media fixture until the mid-nineteenth century.¹¹ In their absence, editors collected information from foreign newspapers, government gazettes, and eyewitness statements.¹² Among the most sought-after eyewitnesses were soldiers who could report what they had seen and experienced while on active service.

Editors did their best to establish networks of correspondents within the military but were primarily reliant on readers to submit letters from friends and family serving overseas.¹³ This pattern reflects the importance of reader contributions in early modern newspapers. Newsgathering in the early modern period was a public, participatory endeavour in which reader submissions played an important part.

⁹ Robert Chapman, *Empire of Normality: Neurodiversity and Capitalism* (London: Pluto Press, 2023), p. ix.

¹⁰ Joad Raymond, *The Invention of the Newspaper: English Newsbooks, 1641-1649* (Oxford: Clarendon Books, 1996), p. 197; Nicholas Brownless, "'News also came by Letters': Functions and Features of Epistolary News in English News Publications of the Seventeenth Century", in *News Networks in Early Modern Europe* (Amsterdam: Brill, 2016), p. 413.

¹¹ Kevin Williams, *A New History of War Reporting* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2020), p. 10.

¹² Jeremy Black, *The English Press in the Eighteenth Century* (London: Routledge, 1987), pp. 61-63.

¹³ Williams, *A New History of War Reporting*, p. 13.

Readers regarded their participation in public debate both as a right that belonged to them as citizens and as a duty that they owed to their community.¹⁴

Some of the letters printed in newspapers contained detailed accounts of military operations. There were no restrictions on soldiers' correspondence until military censorship was introduced towards the end of the nineteenth century, so soldiers could write freely. Despite the risk that post would be intercepted by hostile forces, postal services were maintained even when on campaign in enemy country. Military authorities recognized that relationships with friends and family were critical to preserving morale within the army and did everything they could to facilitate soldiers' correspondence. An Act of 1795, for example, granted cheaper postage to NCOs, seamen, or privates in the armed forces.¹⁵ This Act set an important precedent for the introduction of the Uniform Penny Post in 1840; as one officer phrased it, rank and file soldiers had 'an extraordinary desire of letter-writing', using it for 'giving accounts of the quarters and changes and circumstances that interest them, and a description of places.'¹⁶

The practice of publishing soldiers letters in newspapers was first officially recognized as a problem during the Napoleonic Wars (1803-1815).¹⁷ In nineteenth-century manuals of military law, the General Orders of Arthur Wellesley, future Duke of Wellington (1769-1852), issued at Celorico on 10 August 1810, are usually cited as creating a precedent for the military offence of 'injurious disclosures'.¹⁸ At the time, Wellesley was commanding the army in Portugal. In his General Orders, Wellesley issued a warning to the officers of the army, notifying them that 'the plans of the enemy have been founded on information [...] extracted from the English newspapers; which information must have been obtained through private letters from Officers of the army.'¹⁹

Wellesley's concerns reflect the changing nature of media and communications at the turn of the nineteenth century. As historian Hannah Barker has noted, 'there was a dramatic increase in the number of newspapers produced in England during the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries.'²⁰ This increase, combined with improvements to roads, canals, and postal networks, meant that newspapers were travelling faster,

¹⁴ Hannah Barker, *Newspapers, Politics, and Public Opinion in Late Eighteenth-Century England* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1998), p. 38.

¹⁵ Howard Robinson, *The British Post Office: A History* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1948), p. 157; Catriona Kennedy, *Narratives of the Revolutionary and Napoleonic Wars: Military and Civilian Experience in Britain and Ireland* (New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013), p. 15.

¹⁶ House of Commons, *First Report from the Select Committee on Postage* (London: Stationers Company, 1838), p. 335.

¹⁷ Nicholas Wilkinson, *Secrecy and the Media: The Official History of the United Kingdom's D-Notice System* (London: Routledge, 2009), p. 4.

¹⁸ William Hough, *Precedents in Military Law* (London: W. H. Allen, 1855), p. 155.

¹⁹ John Gurwood, ed., *The General Orders of Field Marshal the Duke of Wellington, K.G., in Portugal, Spain, and France, from 1809 to 1814; in the Low Countries and France, in 1815; and in France, Army of Occupation, from 1816 to 1818* (London: W. Clowes and Sons, 1837) p. 199.

²⁰ Hannah Barker, *Newspapers, Politics and English Society, 1695-1855* (London: Longman, 2000), p. 29.

farther, and in greater numbers than ever before.²¹ The expansion of the press increased the likelihood that newspapers containing military intelligence could be read by hostile states while the intelligence in question was still relevant to ongoing operations.

Even so, controls were slow to be introduced. Rather than forbidding officers from sharing information with their friends of family, Wellesley simply instructed them to be careful. As he put it:

'If they choose to communicate facts to their correspondents regarding the positions of the army, its numbers, formations of its magazines, preparations for breaking bridges, &c., they will urge their correspondents not to publish their letters in the newspapers until it shall be certain that the publication of the intelligence will not be injurious to the army or to the public service.'²²

In other words, military authorities placed their trust in the ability of officers and their families to determine what to reveal, what to conceal, and when. Manuals of military law interpreted this as a presumption in favour of publicity; for example, William Hough, Deputy Judge Advocate General of the Bengal Army and author of a popular manual of military law, described himself as an 'advocate for publicity in all cases', except 'at a moment when it may prove of very dangerous consequences to the situation of an army in the field.'²³

The first explicit prohibitions against soldiers writing to the press were issued to the British East India Company's Bengal Army, but the focus was on military discipline rather than operational security. In General Orders published in Calcutta on 8 June 1822 by Commander-in-Chief Francis Rawdon Hastings, first marquess of Hastings and second earl of Moira (1754-1826), officers were forbidden from submitting anonymous grievances to the press at the risk of being discharged from the service. As this emphasis on 'anonymous grievances' suggests, military authorities in India were not really concerned about the revelation of strategic information; instead, they were worried about insubordination and potential damage to the army's public image. Hastings declared that 'an Officer's thus casting off his just and requisite dependence on his Military Superiors must not be permitted'; he believed that the only outcome of these applications to the press was to 'give a general impression of Inattention, Oppressiveness, or Injustice, in those with whom the Superintendence of such Concerns is Lodged'²⁴

Evidence suggests that many military personnel did not find these justifications convincing. Despite the threat made in General Orders, the prohibition was unsuccessful. Soldiers continued to issue anonymous complaints to the press; they simply withheld their name and contact details from newspaper editors. In their published letters, soldiers justified their behaviour on the grounds that the

²¹ Will Slauter, 'The Rise of the Newspaper', in *Making News: The Political Economy of Journalism in Britain and America from the Glorious Revolution to the Internet* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015), p. 33.

²² Gurwood, *General Orders*, pp. 199-200.

²³ Hough, *Precedents*, p. 189.

²⁴ General Orders, 8 June 1822, British Library, Asia, Pacific and Africa Collections, IOR/L/MIL/17/2/271, p. 161.

hierarchical nature of the army made it necessary to issue their complaints through independent channels; like today, they also worried that making complaints through official channels would negatively affect their professional prospects. As one anonymous letter-writer observed, if a junior submitted a complaint to his senior officer, 'a mark would be placed against his name,' and 'the fear of the latter would deter many from running the risk.'²⁵ Another, writing under the pseudonym Miles Candidus, agreed that 'soldiers are not fond of making themselves publicly known in such cases.'²⁶ Even so, letter-writers argued that the army, just like other branches of the public service, ought to be amenable to public scrutiny. As one letter-writer put it, 'shall the Navy and Army remain, in these liberal days, the only professions which are denied the right of holding injustice and tyranny up to public scorn?'²⁷

In the face of ongoing resistance within the army, authorities in India were increasingly unwilling to enforce the prohibition on submitting complaints to the press. In his Minute on the Press, dated 6 January 1829, Governor-General William Cavendish Bentinck declared that the press in India had been 'of benefit to government and advantage to the community', in that it had 'brought abuses to the notice of government which might otherwise have escaped it.'²⁸ Bentinck did not believe that the press was necessarily a threat to military discipline; instead, it could help to support and strengthen discipline by giving soldiers a platform for making their sentiments known. Although in a Minute on the Press dated 6 September 1830 he requested editors not to publish letters discussing the recent reduction of *batta* (field pay), he identified this request as 'an exception to the general rule'. As Bentinck put it, 'my firm belief is that more good than harm was produced by the open and public declaration of these sentiments of the army', for it provided 'a vent to public feeling'.²⁹

The prevalence of soldiers' letters within the newspapers would once again become matter for comment in Britain during the Crimean War (1853-1856). The Crimean War is often described as the first media war for two key reasons. First, the London *Times* dispatched William Howard Russell (1820-1907) to cover the campaign, making Russell the first professional war correspondent to report directly from the scene of action. Russell subsequently became famous for his exposure of military mismanagement in Crimea, which in turn led to the collapse of the Aberdeen government.³⁰ Second, the expansion of the telegraph system meant that this was the first conflict in which military intelligence could be transmitted instantaneously from the frontlines. As a result, audiences across Europe were able to follow events in Crimea as they unfolded. The conflict was comprehensively covered in the British press, which printed a steady stream of letters from soldiers serving in Crimea.

²⁵ A Sub, 'Military Subjection,' *Calcutta Journal*, 22 March 1823, p. 303-4.

²⁶ Miles Candidus, 'Half-Batta,' *Calcutta Journal*, 2 January 1821, p. 125.

²⁷ Hakim, 'Remarks on Free Press', *Bombay Gazette*, 24 August 1838, p. 1.

²⁸ C. H. Philips, ed., *The Correspondence of Lord William Cavendish Bentinck, Governor-General of India 1828-1835* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1977), 1:136-7.

²⁹ Same as above, p. 505.

³⁰ Joel H. Wiener, *The Americanization of the British Press, 1830s-1914: Speed in the Age of Transatlantic Journalism* (Houndmills, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011), p. 80.

Once again, military authorities were unwilling to intervene directly to control the flow of letters. The detailed coverage of the conflict in British newspapers did raise concerns about operational security; it was widely believed that the Russian czar subscribed to the *Times* and read it every evening. Even so, Russell and his fellow special correspondents were believed to have performed an important democratic function in exposing the army to public scrutiny. As a result, it was only at the very end of the conflict that a new commander, General William Codrington, issued a General Order that warned special correspondents not to publish information that would be useful to the Russians, and threatened to expel them if they did so. The British Army had faced so much criticism for its perceived mismanagement of the war effort that previous commanding officers had felt unable to introduce constraints on the press because they feared that these orders might be interpreted as attempted cover-ups.³¹

Although professional war correspondents would henceforward become a common feature of most military campaigns, soldiers continued to participate in public debate and to shape public attitudes to military campaigns. Their role became particularly important after the introduction of field censorship in the late nineteenth century. These controls were pioneered by Sir Frederick Roberts, first Earl Roberts (1832-1914), who, during the Second Anglo-Afghan War (1878-1880), restricted the number of correspondents who could accompany the force and required telegrams to be formally approved before they were transmitted to Britain.³² As special correspondents were placed under increasing constraints, soldiers saw their letters as a necessary counterpoint to government narratives. For example, after Roberts expelled the accredited correspondents from the campaign in Afghanistan, officers filled the gap by submitting letters to the press in India that described summary executions in Kabul.³³

The turn of the twentieth century witnessed important changes in the history of official secrecy. The Official Secrets Act and the D-Notice system were designed to regulate the behaviour of government officials, military personnel, and newspaper editors. The Official Secrets Act, first introduced in 1889, replaced in 1911, and then amended in 1989, covers a range of offences including the unauthorised communication or receipt of official information. The D-Notice System, a precursor of the modern Defence and Security Media Advisory (DSMA) System, was a voluntary initiative first introduced in 1912 whereby a committee of editors and civil servants issued notices to the press warning them about news that might be injurious to national security if published. These legal and extra-legal measures were justified with reference to growing fears about French and German espionage in the climate of imperial rivalry preceding World War One.³⁴ Historians David Vincent and Christopher Moran have argued that the Official Secrets Act was also informed by the growing number of lower-class employees that had begun to penetrate

³¹ Joseph J. Mathews, *Reporting the Wars* (Westport, CN: Greenwood Press, 1972), p. 74.

³² Williams, *A New History of War Reporting*, p. 55.

³³ Brian Robson, *The Road to Kabul: The Second Afghan War 1787-1881* (London: Arms and Armour Press, 1986), p. 144; 176.

³⁴ Christopher Moran, *Classified: Secrecy and the State in Modern Britain* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012), p. 52.

previously elite government spaces. The changing composition of the civil service, they argue, led authorities to fear that Crown servants could no longer be relied upon to adhere to gentlemanly codes of honour.³⁵

Occurring in the immediate aftermath of these changes, World War One is traditionally seen as the high point of press censorship in Britain; even then, however, soldiers' letters continued to appear in print. Local newspapers were publishing letters from the front that described soldiers' combat experiences. According to historian Helen B. McCartney's study of the Liverpool Territorials, 'the men used the newspapers as another mechanism of communicating with their friends and family and with the wider community'.³⁶ While careful to protect operational intelligence, soldiers shared their perspectives in order to maintain ties with their community and to keep local readers informed.

For every example of a soldier who spoke out, there were probably many more who chose to remain silent. Some complainants indicated that senior officers had tried to deter them from publicizing their grievances through threats or intimidation. Captain William White, for instance, claimed that in 1818 the adjutant general tried to dissuade him from making a complaint on behalf of two Indian officers who had been injured in a hunting accident, warning White that if he persisted 'it would bring upon me the severest displeasure of the government, and be marked in a manner injurious to my future interest.'³⁷ White went ahead and notified authorities, but in some cases these efforts at repression may have succeeded, leaving no historical trace of the abuse.

Even so, the history of the early modern army demonstrates the potential for a different relationship between military personnel and the public. While many military personnel no doubt suffered in silence or kept their conscientious objections to themselves, it is also true that many felt a responsibility to make disclosures in the public interest. These men believed that their profession entailed responsibilities, but did not eliminate their responsibilities as citizens. As one anonymous letter-writer reminded his readers, 'we too (and Heaven forbid that it should be otherwise) have our rights, our priveleges, and our interests.'³⁸

Conclusions

Much has changed since the nineteenth century. We live in an extremely insecure international climate. Society has also been profoundly affected by rapid technological change, including improvements to data storage and sharing that have enabled the instantaneous transmission of large volumes of information. The unregulated nature of the nineteenth century army is no longer appropriate under

³⁵ Moran, *Classified*, p. 25. See also David Vincent, *The Culture of Secrecy: Britain 1832-1998* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1999), pp. 24-25.

³⁶ Helen B. McCartney, *Citizen Soldiers: The Liverpool Territorials in the First World War* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005), p. 115.

³⁷ Captain William White, *A Letter Addressed to the Proprietors of India Stock, Demonstrating British Justice in India* (London: J. Miller, 1823), p. 101.

³⁸ Senex, 'Madras Army', *Calcutta Journal*, 16 October 1819, p. 37.

present circumstances. No one can doubt the need to keep certain information secret in the interests of national security.

Even so, this history has several important implications for the present. At a time when questions are being raised about the ability of the armed forces to foster a speak-up culture, this history demonstrates that in the past military personnel were active participants in public debate. Although soldiers accepted that their unique role carried with it certain obligations towards confidentiality, they also insisted on their identity as citizens, and resisted the idea that the military constituted an entirely distinct category exempt from the usual requirements of openness and accountability.

The reluctance of military authorities to impose constraints on freedom of speech is also a salutary reminder that in the past, military authorities recognized that secrecy could be just as risky as transparency. In the present, political scientists have critiqued a presumption in favour of secrecy, based on the assumption that secrecy is inherently less risky than transparency. As Owen Thomas has emphasized, 'information rights law recognizes the potential harm of disclosure but not the potential harm of secrecy.'³⁹ Secrecy also has social costs, particularly when it comes to fostering relationships of trust. While it is true that states in the past faced a different set of security threats, their unwillingness to contravene press freedoms, even in times of conflict, reminds us not to undervalue the importance of openness and transparency.

The fact that prohibitions, once introduced, were rarely successful is also an important indicator of the limits of legislative change. Legal frameworks can incentivize certain kinds of behaviour but do not always dictate how people behave. These frameworks are most successful if individuals accept the legitimacy of the rules they are being asked to respect. Applying historical perspectives, we see that military personnel were often deeply sensitive to the dangers of leaks and did not disclose risky intelligence willingly. Where leaks happened, it was because people were unconvinced that problems were being addressed or suspected that mismanagement or incompetence was being concealed. As citizens, they felt that they had a responsibility to expose this malfeasance to public scrutiny.

In sum, the history of the early modern British Army reminds us that the distinctions between soldiers and civilians have not always been set in stone. To the contrary, military personnel have historically insisted upon their right, as citizens, to participate in public debate, and to expose military operations to public scrutiny. Clearly, there is a greater need for restrictions on information in the present than there was in the past; yet this history also reminds us that legislative controls are not effective unless they are accepted as legitimate by soldiers themselves. To achieve the appropriate balance between secrecy and transparency requires a combination of cultural, procedural, and legislative reform, all of which must be developed and implemented in consultation with military personnel in order to be successful.

³⁹ Owen Thomas, 'Security in the Balance: How Britain Tried to Keep its Iraq War Secrets', *Security Dialogue* 51, no. 1 (2020), p. 82.

Research Parameters

This briefing is informed by research findings from a two-year postdoctoral project, entitled *Bearing Witness in Wartime: East India Company Soldiers in the British Public Domain, 1750-1857*. In the eighteenth century, a British trading corporation called the East India Company (EIC) began to build a territorial empire in India through a process of violent conquest. To fight these wars of imperial expansion, the EIC formed their own standing armies, which they deployed alongside British Army regiments. Because the EIC's commercial monopoly restricted British access to the subcontinent, these military personnel were an important source of information for domestic audiences in Britain. War correspondents did not yet exist, so soldiers' testimony represented the primary alternative to the official narratives disseminated in government gazettes. Soldiers published books and pamphlets, and their letters appeared in newspapers and periodicals. This project's overall research objective is to determine what soldiers disclosed and what impact this had on contemporary debates about the EIC's military operations.

To achieve this objective, this research critically analyses a combination of print and manuscript materials. Using military records and manuals of military law, it reconstructs the regulatory frameworks in operation in the nineteenth century. Professional conduct within the armies was regulated by the Articles of War laid down by the king or queen, while parliament voted on the Mutiny Act: the code of law that defined and regulated more serious crimes. Supplementing this were orders issued to the army by different authorities including the Secretary of State for War, the Commander in Chief, the Adjutant General and his Deputy, and the Quarter Master General. Using these sources, it becomes possible to understand the incentives and disincentives that informed soldiers' decision to write. Court martial records, read alongside published and unpublished letters authored by soldiers, provide additional insights into their decisions to approach the press with their stories.

The main sources for this project are the writings of soldiers themselves, which took the form of books, pamphlets, and published letters in newspapers and periodicals. To evaluate the impact of these writings on public debate, this project examines how contemporaries responded in editorials and letters to the editor, as well as how soldiers' testimony was cited by EIC shareholders and MPs in parliament. By contrasting soldiers' testimony with official dispatches in government gazettes, it becomes possible to identify how soldiers challenged or supplemented official government narratives. In all, this research demonstrates that soldiers played an important part in the information environment of eighteenth- and nineteenth-century Britain.

Project Identity

Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01

Project Number: 101065824

Project Acronym: WAR_WITNESS

Project Title: Bearing Witness in Wartime: The East India Company's Soldiers in the Public Domain, 1764-1857

Fellow's Name: Dr Callie Wilkinson

Supervisor's Name: Prof Dr Roland Wenzlhuemer

Host Institution: Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich

Time Frame: 1 October 2022 – 30 September 2024